

**The hidden cost of unlabelled seafood:
the risk of consuming unethical and
unsustainable seafood in Europe**

DNA evidence from squid products sold in Italy and Belgium

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Executive summary

Europe is one of the most important consumers of seafood globally, importing almost 70% of its total supply, yet close to half of the products sold on the market are not required to provide any information about the species they contain or their origin. This investigation led by Oceana examined how the lack of labelling requirements for many squid products sold in the European Union (EU) conceals potential links to illegal, unreported, and unregulated (IUU) fishing, human rights abuse, and unsustainable fishing practices. We combined DNA analysis with EU trade data to reveal the hidden risks behind inadequately labelled seafood in Italy and Belgium.

Between March and April 2025, Oceana teams collected 198 squid products sold by supermarkets, fishmongers, and restaurants in Milan and Brussels. Each sample was categorised as fresh or frozen (which are covered by consumer information requirements), prepared and preserved, or sold in restaurants (both exempt from consumer information requirements). The precision of labels was assessed and they were examined for compliance with the EU Common Market Organisation (CMO) Regulation for fisheries and aquaculture products. DNA barcoding and metabarcoding were then used to identify the species, and the genetic results were compared with EU trade data to trace likely origins and identify potential links to high-risk fisheries.

The findings reveal a market with rampant opacity. **Almost half (49%) of the squid products sampled provided no meaningful information on either the species or their catch locations.** Even among products covered by the CMO labelling requirements, compliance was inconsistent. **Out of 198 products sampled, 48 provided information considered precise enough to identify both the species and geographical catch location; among those, 58% were fresh & frozen products, 37% were preserved and prepared products, and 4% were from restaurants.** In restaurants, information was almost entirely absent, even when waiters were queried. These results demonstrate that when labelling is not mandatory, consumers are often left in the dark.

Unlabelled products were dominated by species that can be considered high-risk with respect to illegal or unregulated fishing and labour abuse, depending on their provenance, including jumbo flying squid (*Dosidicus gigas*), Indian squid (*Uroteuthis duvaucelii*), and Argentine shortfin squid (*Illex argentinus*). These species are commonly associated with fleets operating under weak management, limited transparency, and in some cases, documented cases of forced labour and IUU fishing.

Trade data helped explain these results and further shed light on possible risks. Belgium's imports were dominated by China, whose distant-water fleet is the world's largest and primary fishing fleet for jumbo flying squid. Italy sourced most of its squid via Spain, which is the EU's main entry point for squid and also has companies that own or co-own vessels targeting Argentine shortfin squid in the Southwest Atlantic. Additional imports from Argentina, India, Morocco, and Thailand match the species composition found through DNA. Together, these data confirmed that much of the squid sold in Europe, including those found in unlabelled products, comes from distant waters with limited oversight.

This investigation exposes a critical gap in EU seafood transparency rules. While the CMO ensures consumer information for fresh and frozen products, important segments of the market, particularly prepared and preserved products and the food service sector, remain exempt. These loopholes allow seafood from high-risk fisheries to enter the European market, undermining both consumer trust and fair competition with responsible producers.

Oceana calls for a targeted revision of the CMO Regulation to close these gaps. Minimum consumer information on the species, origin, and fishing gear should be mandatory for all seafood products, regardless of processing or point of sale. In addition, Oceana recommends including the flag State of the catching vessel on seafood labels, allowing consumers and relevant stakeholders to know who fished the product.

The results presented here show that without clear labelling, European consumers risk supporting fisheries that deplete oceans and exploit people, while responsible operators face unfair competition. Strengthening seafood labels is both possible and urgently needed to make sure the EU upholds its commitment to strong environmental and fair social standards, and consumers get the information they need to make informed purchasing choices.

Introduction

The European Union (EU) is one of the largest seafood markets in the world and relies largely on imports to meet consumer demand. To protect its citizens, ensure fair competition, and prevent illegally-caught seafood from being sold on the market, the EU has developed a strong legal framework. Traceability and transparency are central to this system, yet loopholes exist.

Under the Common Market Organisation (CMO) Regulation for fisheries and aquaculture products (EU) No 1379/2013, sellers of whole or filleted seafood that is fresh, frozen, or smoked must provide information on the species name, origin, and catching method. Many preserved and prepared items such as battered squid rings, fish fingers, or canned tuna are, on the other hand, exempt from these labelling requirements. Yet these products represent about 27% of fishery and aquaculture products consumed in EU households.¹ Given their popularity, the lack of required information on these products raises concerns, as they may include seafood sourced from fisheries that fail to meet EU environmental and social standards.

A similar lack of transparency affects seafood sold in restaurants, cafeterias, and hotels, which account for roughly 30% of European seafood intake.¹ These establishments are not required to provide information on the species or origin of seafood. As a result, almost half of seafood consumed in Europe reaches people's plates with no information about the specific fish they consume, its source, or how it was caught.

Why squid?

Squid are a diverse group of cephalopods distributed across all oceans. They play a vital role both as predators and prey, including for tuna, cod, seals, whales, and seabirds.^{9,10} Their rapid growth and short lifespan make them generally resilient to environmental changes unless fishing pressure is too high.^{6,11} Depletion of squid stocks can have significant effects on the ecosystem, depriving many predators of a valuable food resource.⁶

Despite their ecological importance and growing role in the global seafood trade, squid fisheries remain mostly unregulated. Few have stock assessments, and many operate in the high seas with little or no management.² This lack of oversight makes them particularly vulnerable to IUU fishing as well as human rights abuses, which have been documented in some distant-water fleets.^{6,7}

Despite these major concerns, the EU imported 79% of the squid it consumed in 2022;³ data from the following year

Among the products affected by these gaps are those containing squid. Squid is traded globally and while its fisheries remain largely unmanaged, global squid fishing has increased 68% from 2017 to 2020.² In Europe, the demand is much greater than the supply, and in 2022, Europe had to import 79% of the squid it consumed.³ Most species are caught without stock assessments and catch limits^{4,5} and sold through opaque supply chains increasingly linked to illegal, unreported, and unregulated (IUU) fishing and serious human rights abuses.^{6,7} Currently, Seafood Watch rates 28 out of 38 assessed squid items as *red* (Avoid), for reasons such as ineffective management, lack of enforcement, violation of regulations, noncompliance, IUU fishing, poor stock conditions, and negative impacts on food webs.⁸

In March and April 2025, Oceana investigated the gaps in information about squid products sold in the EU. Samples were collected from restaurants, supermarkets, and fishmongers in Italy and Belgium and analysed, in partnership with the FishLab, Department of Veterinary Sciences of the University of Pisa, using DNA tools to identify the species. Species identification was used to determine geographical provenance of samples and was compared against trade data to assess risks of association with IUU fishing and human rights abuse. The results highlight the weaknesses in current EU labelling laws and emphasise the need for improved consumer information.

show that Peru was the largest supplier to Europe, followed by the Falkland Islands, India, China, and Morocco.^a Within the EU, Spain is both the main importer of squid and the Member State that catches the largest volumes, targeting the Argentine shortfin squid (*Illex argentinus*) with its long-distance fishing fleet. As a result, most squid consumed in Europe comes from distant waters.

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a. Eurostat ComExt: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/comext/newxtweb/>

EU labelling framework and its gaps

Seafood labelling in the EU is governed by two main regulations that apply both to local and imported products.

The Food Information to Consumers (FIC) Regulation (EU) No 1169/2011 establishes general rules for consumer information, requiring details such as ingredients and food business operators for all food products.

The Common Market Organisation (CMO) Regulation in fishery and aquaculture products (EU) No 1379/2013 adds more specific requirements for seafood. For fresh and frozen seafood products (whether whole or filleted) and some processed items like smoked fish, sellers must provide:

The **commercial designation and scientific name** of the species.

The **production method** (i.e. caught, caught in freshwater, or farmed).

The **catch or production area**, including FAO fishing area.

The type of **fishing gear** used.

Whether the product has been defrosted, and the date of minimum durability.

Methodology

Sampling

In March 2025, Oceana's team visited a total of 14 supermarkets, 13 fishmongers (including those in street markets), and 29 restaurants across the city of Milan, Italy, and collected a total of 100 squid samples.

In March and April 2025, in Belgium, we visited 12 supermarkets, 16 fishmongers, and 31 restaurants across Brussels, collecting a total of 98 squid samples (Fig. 1).

We aimed to obtain a comparable number of samples from three categories:

- Fresh/frozen/whole squid products for which consumer information must be provided on the species, area of origin, and catch method.^c

For prepackaged seafood, the required information must appear on the labels, while for non-prepackaged items, it can be displayed through other means, like billboards or posters.

For prepared and preserved products^b such as battered squid rings, squid balls, paella, etc., this information is not required. This exemption also applies for the food service sector, meaning that restaurants, hotels, and canteens do not have to provide this type of information.¹

- Preserved & prepared products, for which such information is not required.^c (for more information on the classification of products see footnote d)
- Squid sold in restaurants and canteens, where such information is also not required.^c

In total, we sampled:

60 fresh and frozen whole squid products (or unprocessed rings).

72 prepared and preserved products.

66 restaurant dishes containing squid.

b. Prepared and preserved products as listed under the Combined Nomenclature (CN) codes 1604 and 1605:

https://taxation-customs.ec.europa.eu/customs/calculation-customs-duties/customs-tariff/combined-nomenclature_en

c. As outlined in Article 35 of the CMO for fisheries and aquaculture products (EU) No 1379/2013 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2013/1379/oj/eng>

d. For some types of seafood products, it can be impossible to determine whether they should be considered fresh and frozen (chapter 03 of the Combined Nomenclature) and need to adhere to the consumer information requirements (as indicated by the CMO), or whether they are to be considered preserved and prepared (chapter 16 of the Combined Nomenclature). Following information received from the European Commission on October 2025 we understood that, in order to classify a specific "seafood mix" (e.g. a frozen seafood mix product that includes squid, molluscs and shrimps), it is necessary to know whether any ingredient have gone through processing (e.g. cooking, seasoned, heated), and this information is not readily available to consumers. Given that we did not have access to this type of information, we classified frozen seafood mixes as prepared and preserved products (chapter 16 of the CN), which do not require consumer information.

Figure 1. Sampling map (Brussels, Milan)

- Canteen / Restaurant
- Supermarkets
- Fishmongers

- Canteen / Restaurant
- Supermarkets
- Fishmongers
- Street Market

Analysis

● Labels and interpretations

For fresh and frozen products caught locally in waters around Europe (i.e. in the Northeast Atlantic and Mediterranean), the CMO Regulation requires both the name of the FAO sub-area or division (e.g. Subarea 37.2) where the product was caught,^e and the name of such zone expressed in terms that are consumer-friendly (e.g. Central Mediterranean). We established that geographical catch location was provided if at least one of these elements was present. However, a product qualified as being compliant with the CMO only when both types of location information were provided. Although not compliant with the CMO, we also acknowledged that precise geographical information was present when country of origin (e.g. Morocco) or regional names (e.g. Sicily) were indicated.

For packaged products, we examined each label to identify any information on the species and geographical catch location. Similarly, we recorded any information provided, either in writing or orally, by fishmongers and restaurants in response to questions regarding the species and their origins.

The CMO Regulation on consumer information for seafood products requires that both the commercial and scientific names must be displayed. For squid, the accepted commercial name is usually very broad (e.g. "Totano" or "Calamaro" in Italy and "Calamar" in Belgium). We considered that species could be identified if information was provided on the scientific name (e.g. *D. gigas*), the species commercial designation (e.g. Totano gigante del Pacifico), or the common species name (e.g. Humboldt squid). However, we only considered a product to be compliant with the CMO if the scientific name was provided along with any of the accepted commercial names (e.g. *D. gigas* and Totano).

For products fished outside of FAO Area 27 (Northeast Atlantic), we considered that an indication of either the FAO area (e.g. Area 71), the area's name according to the FAO (e.g. Western Central Pacific), or both, constituted compliance with the CMO. Furthermore, we considered that a country's name (e.g. China, Peru, New Zealand), even if not compliant with FAO area names and the CMO, was precise enough to make inferences about geographical catch location. In contrast, any imprecise ocean basin information (e.g. Pacific Ocean, Atlantic Ocean, Indopacific Ocean) was considered uninformative.

e. FAO major fishing areas can be viewed here <https://www.fao.org/fishery/en/area/search>

● Summary of the DNA barcoding & metabarcoding analysis

DNA barcoding is a method used to identify a single species from a tissue sample by sequencing a short, standardised fragment of the DNA. On the other hand, DNA metabarcoding applies this principle to complex mixed samples that may contain many species and uses high throughput sequencing to identify each species. Most of the samples we collected were tissue and contained a single specimen, so they could therefore be analysed using DNA barcoding. However, some samples were composed of a mix of tissues and specimens (for example squid balls) and needed to be analysed using DNA metabarcoding. All DNA analyses were performed by the FishLab, Department of Veterinary Sciences of the University of Pisa.

○ DNA barcoding

For each sample, DNA extraction was conducted according to the salting out procedure described by Armani *et al.* (2014).¹² For amplification and sequencing, the COI gene fragment of ~655 bp was selected and amplified by the universal primer pairs designed by Folmer *et al.* (1994).¹³ In instances where COI barcode amplification or sequencing failed, the analysis was repeated using an alternative 140-220 bp fragment of the 16S rRNA gene with a primer pair designed by Chapela *et al.* (2002).¹⁴ PCR products were sent to an external laboratory for sequencing.

○ DNA metabarcoding

Forty-eight cephalopod products were analysed in duplicate ($n=96$) using DNA metabarcoding, due to their processed nature. Total DNA was extracted with the NucleoSpin Food kit (Macherey-Nagel). The primer pair designed by Chapela *et al.* (2002),¹⁴ which amplifies a fragment of about 190-260 bp (depending on the taxon) of the 16S rRNA, was added to Illumina adapter sequences. DNA Libraries were prepared according to Illumina 16S Metagenomic Sequencing Library Preparation protocol^f and loaded using the MiSeq Reagent Kit v2 (300-cycles).

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● Trade analysis

Trade analysis of squid products was performed using the import-export dataset from the European Market Observatory for Fisheries and Aquaculture Products (EUMOFA).¹⁵ These data covered imports to the EU and intra-EU trade for the period of 2020. It included detailed information on volumes of squid imported into the EU and traded within the EU. Data were also sourced from the ARTIS (Aquatic Resource Trade in Species) database^{g,h}, which aligns FAO production data with UN Comtrade trade data to reconstruct bilateral species-level flows of aquatic foods. ARTIS adjusts for processing and conversion losses to estimate live-weight equivalents. Thus, the import quantities recorded in ARTIS represent estimated live-weight equivalents of traded squid products after back-calculation from product weights using species-specific conversion factors from EUMOFA and national and international government reports. Percentages were calculated as each species' proportion of the total estimated live-weight import volume for 2020, analysed separately for Belgium and Italy.

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f. Retrieved from: https://support.illumina.com/documents/documentation/chemistry_documentation/16s/16s-metagenomic-library-prep-guide-15044223-b.pdf

g. Retrieved from: <https://artisdata.weebly.com/>

h. The ARTIS data was recovered and analysed by MarFishEco Fisheries Consultants Ltd.

Results

Behind the squid labels

● Milan - Italy

Figure 2. Proportion of squid products, divided by categories, that contained some information on either the species or the geographical catch location. This figure does not illustrate the compliance level with CMO requirements.

Out of the 30 fresh and frozen squid products sampled in Milan (for which CMO consumer information is mandatory), 17 provided species-specific information (scientific name and/or commercial name), and 27 provided specific information on the geographical catch location (FAO fishing zone, FAO regional name, country of provenance name) (Table 1). However, only 15 of these products fully complied with the CMO by providing the species' scientific name, the FAO zone (and subarea if relevant), and/or the full regional name.

Overall, 90% of the fresh and frozen squid products that were required to display CMO consumer information provided details on either the species or its geographical catch location. However, only half (50%) fully complied with the CMO. In contrast, just 42% of the prepared and preserved products sampled provided information on either the species (scientific or commercial name) and/or its geographical catch location, a significantly lower rate of informative consumer labels than for fresh and frozen products.

Restaurants showed the lowest level of information provision; only 28% were able to indicate either the species or geographical catch location of the seafood

they sold (Fig. 2). These results clearly illustrate the importance of a strong regulatory framework such as the CMO, which drastically improves the provision of precise consumer information for some types of products; even in the case of fresh and frozen squid products, compliance is only partially achieved.

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Table 1. Squid product samples collected in Milan, Italy, by product type. For each product type, the number of products sampled and successfully analysed for DNA are indicated, along with the numbers of products for which species and/or geographical information was provided.

Italy	Samples collected	Samples with species identified using DNA	CONSUMER INFORMATION	
			Scientific and/or commercial species name*	Specific geographical information**
CMO consumer information required				
Fresh	22	18	10	19
Frozen	8	8	7	8
CMO consumer information not required				
Prepared & preserved	38	33	16	10
Restaurants	32	30	2	9
Total	100	89	33	50

*Scientific name (e.g. *D. gigas*), commercial designation (e.g. Totano gigante del Pacifico), common species name (e.g. Humboldt squid)

**FAO zone number (e.g. FAO 37), FAO major fishing areas by name (e.g. Mediterranean), FAO Divisions (e.g. Adriatic), country of origin (e.g. Morocco) or regional names (e.g. Sicily)

● Brussels - Belgium

Out of the 30 fresh and frozen squid products sampled in Brussels (for which CMO consumer information must be given), only eight provided species-specific information (scientific name and/or commercial name), illustrating a striking rate of non-compliance with the CMO. Twenty of these products provided specific information on the geographical catch location (FAO fishing zone, FAO regional name, country of provenance name) (Table 2), although only ten products fully complied with the CMO requirement for catch area information.

Among prepared and preserved samples 50% provided information on either the species (scientific or commercial name) and/or the geographical catch location. Once again, restaurants were frequently unable to provide information on either the species or specific geographical catch location. Only 35% indicated a geographical origin, and none were able to indicate the species (Fig. 2). These results highlight clear discrepancies in CMO compliance rate between Member States but nonetheless reinforce the need for a strong regulatory framework on seafood labels. Although products subject to the CMO generally displayed more informative labels or claims than those outside its scope, full compliance was lacking for most products where CMO requirements applied.

Overall, 67% of the fresh and frozen squid products that needed to display CMO consumer information provided information on either the species or its geographical catch location. Only 27% of these products fully complied with the CMO, a lower compliance rate than in Italy.

Table 2. Squid product samples collected in Brussels, Belgium, by product type. For each product type, the number of products sampled and successfully analysed for DNA are indicated, along with the numbers of products for which species and/or geographical information was provided.

Belgium	Samples collected	Samples with species identified using DNA	CONSUMER INFORMATION	
			Scientific and/or commercial species name*	Specific geographical information**
CMO consumer information required				
Fresh	24	22	4	14
Frozen	6	6	5	6
CMO consumer information not required				
Prepared & preserved	34	27	16	9
Restaurants	34	32	0	12
Total	98	87	24	47

*Scientific name (e.g. *D. gigas*), commercial designation (e.g. Totano gigante del Pacifico), common species name (e.g. Humboldt squid)

**FAO zone number (e.g. FAO 37), FAO major fishing areas by name (e.g. Mediterranean), FAO Divisions (e.g. Adriatic), country of origin (e.g. Morocco) or regional names (e.g. Sicily)

● Overall labelling results

Out of 198 products sampled, 48 provided information considered precise enough to identify both the species and its geographical catch location (58% were fresh & frozen products, 37% were preserved and prepared products, and 4% were from restaurants).

About 49% of the squid products sampled did not provide any useful information that would permit the identification of the species or where they came from (22% of fresh and frozen products, 54% of preserved and prepared products, and 68% of restaurant dishes) (Fig. 3).

Squid found in prepared and preserved products and in restaurants were, for the most part, not labelled and no information was provided on either the species or the geographical catch location.

Figure 3. Relative proportion of products sampled in Italy and Belgium which indicated the species name (scientific, common, or commercial designations) and specific geographical area (FAO zone number, FAO zone name, regional seas name and/or country of origin name). Proportions are indicated for each type of sampled product: frozen or fresh products (which need to provide CMO consumer information) and prepared and preserved products and products sold in restaurants (which are not required to provide CMO consumer information).

What DNA reveals

The genetic analysis conducted by the FishLab, Department of Veterinary Sciences of the University of Pisa successfully identified nearly all the squid products down to species level using either barcoding or metabarcoding. A few samples had to be removed from further analysis due to:

- low quality reads (3 samples);
- a possible sampling error (i.e. the tissue sampled did not belong to squid) (13 samples); and
- identification only to the genus level (5 samples, all of which were *Illex* spp.).

All samples retained for analysis were either wholly squid or contained squid as part of a mixture (i.e. in preserved and prepared products) and had relatively high-quality barcoding or metabarcoding reads.

Full details of the species identified through DNA analysis are provided in the Annex.

● Not-so-local 'local' squid

The Oceana team collected 39 samples from Brussels and Milan which allegedly originated from local fishing grounds, such as the Northeast Atlantic (FAO 27) and the Mediterranean (FAO 37). Five of those samples were removed, as four could only be identified as

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Illex spp., preventing determination of the geographical provenance, and one was identified as cuttlefish, likely due to a sampling error. Out of the 34 remaining samples with robust DNA results, 24 were found to be incorrectly attributed to 'local' waters.

In fact, about 71% of the samples that were claimed to originate from the Northeast Atlantic Ocean or the Mediterranean Sea were actually species from the Pacific Ocean or the Southwest Atlantic Ocean.

It should be noted that these results are conservative given that one of the species we considered as local, European squid (*Loligo vulgaris*), is also extensively caught off the west coast of Africa and frequently imported from Morocco.

Our DNA analysis reveals widespread mislabelling of squid sold as “local”. In reality, the vast majority of squid consumed in Europe is caught in distant waters and is part of an opaque global trade network that can sometimes hide serious cases of IUU fishing and human rights abuse.^{6,7} Yet, consumers consistently favour locally sourced foods,¹⁶ this is well reflected in Eurobarometer studies stating that “everywhere in the EU, consumers show a strong preference for regional, national or EU products”¹⁷ and that consumers continue to value information on the species and origin of the product.¹⁸

Whether their motivation in buying ‘local’ is to support local businesses, strengthen local coastal fishing communities, or reduce environmental impacts, buyers favouring European squid may not realise they are often served a product caught on the other side of the world and traded through complex global supply chains.

● Prepared, preserved and... hidden

Nearly half of the products (49%) simply did not have any useful labels indicating key fisheries parameters such as species and origin. This practice is currently legal for a large proportion of seafood products, namely prepared and preserved products which are exempt from the CMO consumer information requirements, and for restaurants which are not required to provide consumer information.

Strikingly, our analysis revealed that out of the 83 products for which squid species were identifiable using DNA and which lacked species or provenance information, 94% contained squid from distant waters, such as Southeast Asia, the Pacific or Southwest Atlantic Ocean (Fig. 4).

This means that consumers are not only left in the dark regarding many squid products but are also unknowingly consuming squid originating from faraway fisheries, with potential problems related to management, lawfulness, and human rights.

This consumer preference and disconnect between offer and demand might explain why many products were falsely claimed to have been local. In restaurants, a general lack of knowledge among sellers, particularly servers, might also explain the misrepresentation observed.

Figure 4. The geographical origin of 83 sampled squid products for which no consumer information was available regarding species and/or catch location, as evidenced by DNA barcoding and metabarcoding.

— Provenance of the squid with no labels —
(based on the number of squid identified using DNA)

The lack of proper labelling hides the true diversity of squid species that are sold on the EU market. To evaluate whether the number of species declared by retailers and restaurants matched those identified through DNA analyses, we compared the number of species listed on packaging or declared by restaurant staff with those identified through DNA analysis. Overall, we identified 15 different squid species across all samples using DNA analysis compared with nine species listed or claimed

in total (**Annex**). Restaurants sold the widest variety of species ($n=10$) yet provided the least information, with staff mentioning only two species across all 60 restaurants surveyed (**Fig. 5**). Interestingly, although the diversity of species present on the market was not reflected through labels or claims, an unmarketed species was mistakenly declared. Indeed, one brand sold in a Brussels supermarket labelled a pack of squid rings as *Architeuthis* sp., a giant squid genus that is not commercially traded.

Figure 5. The number of species declared on squid product labels or indicated in restaurants, compared to the number of squid species identified in the products using DNA tools.

● Where do squid sold in Europe come from?

The squid trade is a fast-growing, constantly evolving sector that often links distant waters to international markets. Its global nature, the opacity of its supply chains, and the many actors involved in its distribution can make it difficult to trace squid products back to their source of origin. In this trade, both the geographical catch location and the origin of the fleet targeting the squid are important as some fleets have been associated with severe instances of human rights abuse and illegal fishing.^{2,5,6} In Belgium, most squid imports in 2024 came from China, whereas in Italy, most of the squid on the market were imported from Spain, with some important international players such as India, Morocco, Thailand, and Argentina (**Fig. 6**). Spain acts as the primary trader of squid in Europe: it has a large long-distance fishing fleet which catches squid in international waters, namely in the Southwest Atlantic Ocean, and in 2024, it imported a substantial volume of squid from abroad, namely from the Falkland Islands, Morocco, India, and China. Spanish companies also own vessels that catch squid

while flagged to Argentina and the Falkland Islands, both major suppliers to the Spanish market. As a result of this complex trade, and due to a lack of public information on the country of registration of fishing vessels (i.e. the flag State) supplying squid to Europe, it is practically impossible for consumers and interested parties to identify which nation has fished the squid products they purchase. Similarly, squid imported into the EU from China could have been caught by any fleet anywhere in the world, as the trade data do not include information on where these imports were caught or by whom.

Trade data indicated that a slightly higher diversity of squid species is sold on the Italian market compared to Belgium. Total volumes of squid imported by Italy in 2024 (87 285 tonnes) were significantly higher than for Belgium (3 438 tonnes) and exhibited some notable differences in the species traded, which are also reflected in our DNA results. Namely, Belgium primarily imported *Dosidicus gigas*, the jumbo flying squid (also called Humboldt squid), which originates from the Southeast Pacific and is extensively fished within South American national waters by Chile, Ecuador, and Peru, and outside national waters by fleets from East Asia (China, Japan, South Korea and Taiwan). These trade data closely match our DNA results (Fig. 7) which show the importance of jumbo flying squid on the Belgian seafood market compared to other squid species. In contrast, the Italian squid trade involves a larger number of species, with the two most imported species, Patagonian squid

(*Doryteuthis gahi*) and Argentine shortfin squid (*Illex argentinus*) originating from the Southwest Atlantic Ocean where they are targeted by South American, European, and East Asian fleets. This trend was also observed in our DNA results, which highlight that no one species dominated the market in Milan, although we also noted the presence of jumbo flying squid, Indian squid (*Uroteuthis duvaucelii*), and European squid (*L.vulgaris*). Trade data indicate that Morocco is a relatively recent trade partner of Italy (post-2018), corresponding to the presence of European squid which may be mistaken as local in cases where it is caught by non-EU fleets off the coast of west Africa.

Given the importance of Spain as an inter-EU trading country for squid, and the fact that the majority of squid on the Italian market was imported from Spain, we investigated squid imports into Spain to evaluate whether these could explain some of the results we observed in Italy (Fig. 6). The significant imports of squid by Spain from the Falkland Islands, whose fleet mainly targets Patagonian squid, likely explains the dominance of that species in the Italian products we analysed. In the case of Argentine shortfin squid, its importance on the Italian market could reflect the fact that it is targeted by the Spanish fleet, while the sale of products containing jumbo flying squid could potentially be Spain's imports from China.

Figure 6. Relative importance of exporting countries, visualized on a map and indicated as percentages of 2024 squid imports by a) Belgium, b) Italy, and c) Spain, based on EUMOFA trade data, and d) visualized together in a bar graph.

Main Exporting Countries for **Belgium's** Squid Imports (2024)

Main Exporting Countries for **Italy's** Squid Imports (2024)

Main Exporting Countries for **Spain's** Squid Imports (2024)

d) Bar graph

● A high-risk trade with no labels: genetics reveal problematic species

Food labels empower consumers and allow them to make informed purchasing choices. They also provide interested third parties such as authorities, researchers, NGOs, and journalists, with valuable information that can be verified or used for trade and market analyses. Without mandatory labelling, the need for robust traceability breaks down, and it becomes difficult to hold producers accountable. Food labels on the type and origin of a product should be a minimum transparency standard for all food products, including all seafood products, no matter where they are sold.

Contrasting our DNA results with EUMOFA trade data from 2024 offers some important insights into the possible origin of squid found in Brussels and Milan. Our DNA analyses revealed that squid in unlabelled products came primarily from abroad: the most commonly found species was jumbo flying squid, followed by Indian squid and Patagonian squid (Fig. 7). These results aligned with trade statistics indicating the importance of China, whose long-distance fishing fleet extensively targets jumbo flying squid, and India as exporters of squid to Belgium. In the case of Italy, trade data highlighted India and Spain as major exporters; Spain, in turn, imported squid primarily from the Falkland Islands, whose fleet mainly targets Patagonian squid. Although trade data fluctuate from year to year, 2020 Artis dataⁱ on the trade of squid species to Italy and Belgium reflected

similar trends, with jumbo flying squid, Patagonian squid, and Argentine shortfin squid accounting for most squid imports into Italy and Belgium. However, Indian squid was not present in the 2020 species trade data, possibly because the squid trade with India is relatively recent (Fig. 8).

i. Retrieved from: <https://artisdata.weebly.com/>

Figure 7. Proportion of different squid species belonging to seafood products sampled in Brussels and Milan, as identified using DNA analysis.

DNA results (2024)

Figure 8. Proportion of different squid species belonging to seafood products imported into Italy and Belgium in 2020 as reflected by the ARTIS dataset.

Trade data (2020)

In the absence of informative labels, clear risks arise with respect to the origin and mode of production. In fisheries, and particularly high-risk fisheries such as squid fisheries, this includes the risk of products being derived from IUU fishing or being directly linked to instances of human rights abuse. Although it is difficult to assess whether the squid that China exported was actually caught by Chinese fishing vessels, its importance as a squid trader with Belgium and the dominance of jumbo flying squid in our samples from Brussels raises significant concerns about potential links to fisheries characterised by IUU fishing and human rights abuse. Jumbo flying squid is the most traded squid species in the world and is one of the main targets of the Chinese long-distance fishing fleet.¹⁹ China now owns some of the world's leading distant-water fishing fleets, with operations around the globe.^{20,21} Some of these fleets, have been associated with severe instances of human rights abuse, and illegal and unregulated fishing.^{6,7,22} The Chinese fleet targeting jumbo flying squid is particularly notorious for grave human rights abuse, including the deaths of crew members who are sometimes enslaved and forced to stay at sea for months or years.^{7,22,23} The presence of jumbo flying squid potentially originating from China on the European market therefore raises grave concerns and must be addressed urgently, beginning with increased transparency on the composition and origin of seafood products.

Our study highlights how species with a known risk of being associated with IUU fishing and human rights abuse can be sold in Europe without any labels on what they are, where they come from, and who fished them. This underscores the importance of mandatory consumer information for seafood that not only includes the species and its geographical origin, which should be a minimum requirement, but also the nationality of the fleet that caught it.

Similarly, many of the specimens from unlabelled packages were identified as Indian squid, which is an Indo-West Pacific species and is important for Chinese, Indian, and Thai fisheries. Given its distribution, this species has a high risk of being associated with extended periods at sea (months to a year), as well as illegal and largely unregulated fishing activities.^{2,19} The role of India and Thailand as major exporters of squid to Italy matches with the presence of this species on the Italian market (Fig. 6).

Illustrating the truly global nature of the squid trade, the next most common species in unlabelled products were Patagonian squid and Argentine shortfin squid, which are targeted on the high seas by long-distance fishing vessels, including those from Europe, South America, and Asia. For example, both of these species are targeted by major Spanish operators, including Spanish-owned vessels operating through joint ventures and subsidiaries. Of particular concern is the high-seas fishery for Argentine shortfin squid just outside of Argentinian waters, which is unmanaged and unregulated, and is tightly linked with high risks of human rights abuse and forced labour aboard some Chinese vessels.⁶

Half of the squid products we sampled in Brussels provided no information on the species or the geographical area, leaving consumers largely in the dark about what they are consuming. Perhaps more worryingly, 50% of the products sold fresh by fish mongers provided no information whatsoever, showing a blatant disregard for the CMO requirements for consumer information. These products were composed mostly of the high-risk jumbo flying squid.

Conclusion

This investigation suggests that a lack of transparency is hiding the true cost of seafood consumed in Europe. Due to relatively lax regulations on the labelling of certain fisheries and aquaculture products, almost half of seafood eaten in Europe reaches consumers' plates with no information about the specific seafood products they consume, their sources, or how they were caught.

This is reflected in our finding that nearly half (49%) of the products we sampled provided no useful information on species or origin, and these were precisely the products in which the highest risk species were found. While 37% of preserved and prepared products voluntarily provided information on the species and its origin, only 4% of restaurants were able to do so. Yet, behind insufficiently labelled squid dishes and products lie a complex global supply chain tainted with illegal and unregulated fishing, human rights abuse, and severe environmental consequences.

Our DNA analyses also revealed that the diversity of species sold on the market is misrepresented, with 15 species identified using genetic tools compared to nine declared species. Furthermore, DNA evidence confirms that much of the squid sold as "local" or without clear

origin is in fact caught thousands of kilometres away, often by fleets operating under opaque and high-risk labour conditions.

The DNA findings aligned with recorded trade flows into Europe. China and India acted as key suppliers to Belgium, while Spain, the EU's gateway for squid, substantially imported from the Falkland Islands and supplied Italy with the majority of the squid present on its market. Combining trade data with genetic evidence indicated that unlabelled squid products sold in Belgium and Italy could originate from highly problematic fisheries that have been repeatedly flagged for regulatory gaps, a lack of management, IUU fishing exposure, and documented labour abuses.

These findings expose a major gap in the EU's seafood labelling system: while some products must disclose the species they contain and their origins, others, namely prepared, preserved, and restaurant-served seafood meals, do not. Without information on the species, its origin, and the flag State that caught it, consumers risk supporting a trade they would otherwise reject, and unethically sourced products will continue to enter the EU market.

Recommendations

To address the lack of transparency around seafood products sold in the European Union, which undermines the fair competition with EU producers and puts consumers at risk, Oceana recommends a targeted revision of the Common Market Organisation (CMO) Regulation for fishery and aquaculture products:

Require basic information such as species, origin, fishing gear and production method for all seafood products, removing current exemptions for prepared or preserved fish, crustaceans, molluscs, and caviar.

Require the food service sector (such as restaurants, hotels, and mass caterers) to provide this basic information about seafood (species, origin, fishing gear, and production method) to their customers.

Require wild-caught seafood products to specify the flag State: the country of registration of the fishing vessel.

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Annex

- ④ All squid species identified using DNA barcoding and metabarcoding, the number of samples in which they were identified, and their geographical distribution according to Sea Life Base <https://www.sealifebase.se/search.php>¹
- ④ All maps are generated using Aquamaps 2019²

Scientific name	Vernacular name (English)	Number of specimens identified through DNA analysis - Milan	Number of specimens identified through DNA analysis - Brussels	Species/Genus indicated on labels or claims?	Species/Genus identified using DNA tools?	Distribution Map
<i>Doryteuthis gahi</i>	Patagonian squid	24	8	Yes	Yes	
<i>Dosidicus gigas</i>	Jumbo flying squid	22	48	Yes	Yes	
<i>Uroteuthis duvaucelii</i>	Indian squid	16	5	Yes	Yes	
<i>Illex argentinus</i>	Argentine shortfin squid	10	9	Yes	Yes	
<i>Loligo vulgaris</i>	European squid	10	6	Yes	Yes	
<i>Illex coindetii</i>	Shortfin squid	4	0	Yes	Yes	
<i>Uroteuthis singhalensis</i>	Long barrel squid	2	1	No	Yes	

(continued on next page)

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Scientific name	Vernacular name (English)	Number of specimens identified through DNA analysis - Milan	Number of specimens identified through DNA analysis - Brussels	Species/Genus indicated on labels or claims?	Species/Genus identified using DNA tools?	Distribution Map
<i>Uroteuthis chinensis</i>	Mitre squid	2	1	Yes	Yes	
<i>Uroteuthis edulis</i>	Swordtip squid	1	2	Yes	Yes	
<i>Loligo reynaudii</i>	Cape Hope squid	1	0	No	Yes	Southeast Atlantic Ocean, South Africa
<i>Loliolus beka</i>	Beka squid	1	0	No	Yes	
<i>Doryteuthis opalescens</i>	Opalescent inshore squid	0	3	No	Yes	
<i>Illex illecebrosus</i>	Northern shortfin squid	0	1	Yes	Yes	
<i>Ommastrephes bartramii</i>	Neon flying squid	0	2	No	Yes	
<i>Sthenoteuthis oualaniensis</i>	Purpleback flying squid	0	2	No	Yes	
<i>Architeuthis</i> sp.	Genus: Giant squid	0	0	Yes	No	

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